

Transforming Small Local Business To Widely Recognized Brands

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Abstract:- From seeing changes in economy to polity to technological advancements, we see growth in each field. Growing and getting reached is making people fulfill their desire. This study examines the brief detailing of how organizations go global from local. Starting a venture brings a lot of hopes with it, from providing employment to people, to making need of people fulfilled, making use of resources and many more. With all this they need development, development in the sense to be RECOGNIZED ACROSS THE GLOBE. For setting up recognition we need to be perfect all-errands and be ready to accept the upcoming opportunities.

Keywords:- Globalization, Resources, Venture, Layout, Opportunities.

I. INTRODUCTION

“Globalization” the term that defines all those process across the globe incorporated in a single manner. It can also be defined as opening of wider look over local, national to international market by sharing goods, capital, equity, economy, ideas from different countries for operational efficiency. Globalization, if implemented properly, can result over a more equitable world where there would an equal distribution between rich and poor. Sooner or later, we could see a world with no discrimination. Looking to the contrary side, there could see a serious impact over globe where the weak community are subdued over the strong. Removing such barriers could also make the countries stable, and also, they would look forward for being called developed over developing country.

The global changes in the world, it's economy, polity, business development skills, technological advancement and much more are now no more the same, we don't see the same era. Now it's the era of bringing desire into action. It's not just to sit and work for the assigned work, either looking forward for new advancements. Bringing a change within, organization and surrounding is what one need to focus. The amount of contribution we provide we get it back; it might be of any form. Organizations are now trying and must try to change their strategies and move on out of borders of countries, not just states. From the demand of cheaper resources to competitive market to focusing on alternatives and targeting global markets and setting a purpose of working, shows the emotion to grow the business worldwide. Today's business environment is no more back with old beliefs, barriers of not exchanging of ideas between different levels organization are removed now. Everyone tries to work united with a team spirit. Consistency towards the work will make you reach greater heights. How to get consistency? Motivation is the key factor behind consistency. An employee needs to be motivated each moment to give back the worth. The state of expansion,

‘Going Global’ can be turned to ‘Being Global’ by integration and optimization of performance. According to Friedman, (2006) “The World is Flat” it means that “the global competitive playing field is being levelled”, it's now definitely possible for more people to compete and collaborate .In other words, we see a world being more global than ever. In just few spans of time we can shift from one country to other, we can be everywhere and anywhere. Gone are the days when people used to be idle, waiting for someone to push, people are trying themselves to be motivated and move ahead. We need to be ready to face the situation, every moment comes up with a new opportunity. The best example, the pandemic situation (Covid 2020-2021) which just haven't changed the life of a common man, had brought a diverse change in multinational brands. Some took it as opportunity and grown, while other still struggling. This period brought a diverse change in work environment, the sudden lockdown made the office workers to work remotely and they are doing their best. We don't know about the next moment, what miracle it would bring to us. Be ready to face any situation. If you fail, it will teach you lesson to do better next.

International business can be interaction of an individual, colleagues, its organization and among different countries. International business comprises of all commercial transactions, irrespective of private/government, sales, investments, tariffs, transportation etc. exchanged between two or more countries. To reach to an international position, one has to begin from local market checking over quality and consistency of production. Slowly and gradually start expanding the business. Because we couldn't reach top floor with climbing stairs. Customer's review and satisfaction matters a lot. The strategy needs to upgraded by proper study on product's review and the need of market and upgrading skills. This study would help small and medium business to move from baby steps to walk and run in the market by upgradation. Companies which are present there for a long time, and have significant competitive advantages, and therefore they offer more experience to that market, there can be a huge amount of risk to firm cultural differences, which should be in place ahead of embarking those markets. Martin and Chney (2006), organizations (Including their leaders and management) need to create environmental competence in order to realize the needs and wants of global marketing, by creating an ambiance of analytic competence to be able to evaluate global marketing.

This particular research focuses on some of the organizations who have used certain strategies, systems, values, processes, structure which help us to understand how they were successful when they entered the global market.

II. OBJECTIVES

- To study the strategy and action taken by companies to go global.
- To know challenges faced by companies to reach out globalization.
- To observe the methodology of changed scenario of workspace.

III. METHODOLOGY

The data for the study was obtained from existing literature on how going global is beneficial of growth of organization and its support to nation's growth. The data was also collected from literature related to different organization's work culture after being global and their journey from local to global. The study purely relies on different studies made earlier with respect to the content required.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Ferns And Petals

India being a country with a rich variety of culture, tradition and respect for others has a custom to offer flower as a token of love, it may be in any form. With the change in economic and social reforms there was also a change in mindset of people which brought a change in the society.

Today, what we see as the largest floral retail chain of India, Ferns and Petals (FNP) was then started by Mr. Vikas Gutgutia when he went to meet his girl-friend Meeta and saw the situation of the capital city having no good flower shop. He belonged to a family which dealt with flowers and the situation faced by him was a turning point in his life and he started FNP with just an amount Rs 5,000 in the year 1994 and I guess he might never have thought of such growth within such a small time-gap.

The days passed by and Vikas faced a phase where the expansion of business was to the pan India. As the world was turning to technology the owner thought to start selling flowers online and adding new varieties of flowers and also gift items. This company has redefined flower and gifting business.

A normal man can never ever think of what he did and also, he made the use of opportunity and worked hard in right time and whatever he is today is because of his dedication and hard work. He brought up an unorganized sector into market and that too made it possible to serve globally.

It was to break the myth that flowers can only be sold by sitting in the store and also to multiple stores and larger impact.

Experience is the best way to have a new journey or stand up again in the lost journey. The owner of FNP with a great success now, went through worst in his life but never gave up and now he is the one who is one of the leading e-commerce business owners. Gutgutia has his share of failures. One of his ventures, in his words was "absolutely

disastrous", placed in a foray into street foods, Riding on the success of FNP, five years ago Gutgutia began a venture called 'Chatak Chaat,' a chain serving north Indian street foods. "I thought I had another brand up my sleeve...I if I could do magic with flowers, I could do the same with chaat. But the venture failed and it has been my biggest lesson in business," he says. The failed venture resulted in a loss of about Rs 25 crore for Gutgutia.

B. Transformation Of Business Model:

Mr. Gutgutia just started with a flower shop and then added cards, gifts, cakes, chocolates. And now is ready with ventures of events, weddings, franchising, gardening, designing hub, handicrafts etc.

C. Marketing Strategy:

In India we love to gift people in every now and then. FNP look forward every time to provide special discounts, coupons, combo packs, fast delivery and make their customers satisfied with their product and makes assurance that they would have next shopping back there. Ferns N Petals is the most rapidly growing floral chains in India, which has expanded its reach in about 120 cities through 300 retail outlets pan India.

Mr. Gutgutia had set a great example that how we can make our resources into use, he used the nature(flowers) to grow his business model. I think he might never have thought flowers shop would one day into such a big venture. This is all because of their online presence, because online stores are more beneficiary for both buyers and sellers. Also, his journey teaches that no amount of money is less to start a business if you have a BURNING DESIRE to do it and no work is big or small. He learnt from his failures. Now, FNP's revenue is about \$28.3M.

FNP is ready always for special occasion and festivals to provide them the most with the best, they also add items according to this special occasions.

During covid times as we couldn't celebrate occasions with our loved ones, ferns and petals was ready with the contactless delivery system to not to disappoint any of the customers which increased the trust of buyers over FNP and their revenue increased by 40-45%. I was visiting the ferns and petals official website just 2 days back and I saw that they are all set for Father's Day which is coming up next week, and it's all set for Rakhi which is about 2 months and they started a good way to market it. So, they are well prepared every now and then. They also offer personalized gifts which has now become a trend to gift, it means its ready to go with the trend. A good business man always goes with trend with different marketing strategies. Ferns N Petals has expanded its international footprints into the South East Asia and Middle East. In addition to a physical presence, with two stores in UAE and one in Singapore, they also have built a strong online presence with separate websites in Qatar and Saudi Arabia.

D. Balaji Wafers

It's rightly said that a failure teaches a good lesson to the people and make them such strong to fight with any situation in future. A farmer hand with working day and

night in the fields thought to shift to Rajkot in search of work, the struggling period of their life. The three Veerani brothers with their hardworking nature and honesty within them joined a canteen in the year 1974 in cinema theatre of Rajkot where they sold homemade wafers and sandwiches made by their wives, they shifted city by selling their old piece of land at INR 20,000. Time passed by and owner handed over the canteen to the brothers and they continued the same over 15 years, day by day their sells started increasing and they also started selling around Rajkot, and saw that people loved the taste of handmade foods and thought to establish a plant in 1995 to produce in huge quantity in affordable price and stand up in the market in a wider manner. But they had to face a lot of troubles, but their patience and perseverance made them a success one. They used to move from shops to shops and sell it, some shopkeepers denied taking in bulk, some complained of products, but they never got se-motivated, they worked harder and harder. With its success in 1999 it took next step to establish fully automatic machine to produce wafers. Simultaneously he captured entire market of Gujarat and shifted to produce in others states and slowly established other manufacturing units. The main motive was to make the taste of home in everyone's mouth. Now in the present situation it is the most trusted brand (many big companies want to have joint venture or want to take it over because of its taste and pricing structure) and starting selling globally because of its quality as well as quantity.

The journey from working on bare land to the owner of the Balaji wafers pvt. Ltd., was not so easy. The hurdles brought more courage, it created more sense of responsibility, it taught many lessons and we can see the result directly today. From my personal experience with Balaji wafers products, I say it's too satisfying for the customers and yes can feel it's competency with other wafers brands like Haldirams, Bikaji etc. Customers love and support is what makes an organization successful, the kind of response Balaji wafers received in Rajkot then to complete Gujarat, then transforming to nearby states Maharashtra, Rajasthan and now pan India as well as exporting to foreign countries. Why did customers support them? It is all because of the organizations hard work, the quality they produce. Economic times has recognized Balaji wafers as the 'SULTAN OF WAFERS' and international magazine i.e., Asia Pacific Food Online published a special article with 'CHIP OFF THE OLD BLOCK'. Balaji wafers is also the member of snack food association. India Snacks Market is growing due to following factors Lifestyle Changes, Rising Urbanization, Growing Middle Class Population, Local Availability and Availability of Snacks in Small Package Size, Low Price and Company's Strategies to focus on regional taste. Apart from taste, color, hygiene, health concern and price its quantity and crunchiness in the products are the key factors for attractiveness for customers.

India snacks market is segmented into a rich variety of namkeen, wafers, chips, and all other munching snacks. Looking over market value share, Namkeen has the highest market share compared to all other segments. At present, in both organized and unorganized market, Namkeen is the leading segment. Balaji wafers follow line and staff type of

organization. It basically shows their proper structure of following up from ground to upper level and vice-versa. By this method every single individual is connected to each other. BALAJI WAFERS PVT. LTD. To reduce the wastage and control production they Produce the products after receiving the order from the dealers. Repairs and maintenance are very essential part of the production management. We have seen the entire scenario of the production is depended on the machines and plant, one has to make sure that they are well maintained and equipped with daily's tasks, each day's production matters a lot. here is systematic repairs and maintenance of the plant of the unit, as all the production work is done by it. To look after plant and other various component of the same, Company has hired some technicians which would help them out. "Kataria Enterprise", Balaji Wafers clearing and forwarding agent.

E. Organization Structure

F. Competitors:

- PepsiCo India
- Parle
- Haldirams
- ITC
- Euro India Fresh Food Ltd.
- Gopal Namkeen
- Bikanervala
- DFM Foods
- Diamond
- Kellogg's

G. Process Layout Of Balaji Wafers Pvt.Ltd.

H. Dr. Reddy's Laboratories

There was a time when India used to import all the medicines from other countries except basic medicines like cough, allergy, fever. Foreigners started calling India as "copycat" because Indian pharma used to copy imported medicines by reverse engineering. To break this stereotype Indians started thinking to explore more and start production in the country by own research and the big hand behind such thought was Mr. Kalam Anji Reddy. The Vivekanand of new generation, he used to read things and grasp and fix it at once. After schooling he completed his BSC in pharma and PhD in fine chemicals and worked in a company for 6 years and got experience in this field. He saw the opportunity and left the job in 1974 and made his made medicine i.e., Metronidazole and then continued making some more but all off those were copied by reverse engineering and it doesn't give satisfaction to Mr. Reddy and thus in the year 1984 in Hyderabad to cater the needs of Pharma sector in India. He started by taking loan of 25 lakh and his savings from old job and with an aim that India should produce medicine by its own research. The first medicine made by them was Methyldopa, but during the initial stage they faced many problems. He planned a strategy to compete with his competitors in the market by selling the same dose of medicine in half the price of other brands so as to stand in the market with consistency. Then, he continued same strategy and made continuously many medicines in affordable price and stated growing rapidly in the market. Now in the present scenario we can see it as global presence in more than 100 countries, with subsidiaries in the US, UK, Russia, Germany and Brazil; joint ventures in some countries like South Africa, China and Australia; representative offices in 16 different countries and third-party distribution set ups in 21 countries. Continuing the spirit of good business man with extravagant strategies he received many awards and now is the leading producer in pharma sector.

I. Raymond

Raymond, the man itself gives a complete picture of a man's attire from normal shirts, pants to wedding suits. They started their journey in 1925 by setting up a woolen mill, after which brought changes in cloth making industries. It came up with many strategies to change the style of a knitting the cloths and made the machines to the advanced one. They established readymade garment plant in various places so as to meet the demand of fabrics. The owner of Raymond says "The organization produces high-valued pure-wool, wool-blended and premium polyester viscose worsted suiting with an addition to half a million blankets and shawls to their products. Our strong in-house skills for research and development have always resulted in path-breaking new products raising the standard of the Indian textile industry." The owner didn't keep himself just to cloth market but also charter airplane services, Prophylactics including Surgical Gloves, Engineering includes Files, Auto-Components, Agri tools, Cutting Wools and Hand Tools, Toiletries and Cosmetics. Slowly added denim, polyester and others, to make its market with many varieties. 'The Complete Man' the tagline is a very successful tag line in advertisement arena. It targeted customers of various ages and over all occupation people. The officer became his favorite part of customers because they require new suite every next day. Raymond shows its presence both in international and domestic market with equal amount of success. The company is a major supplier of complete range of garments and fabrics to the textile industry in nearly 50 countries in Europe, Japan, Middle East, and North America.

J. Rationale

Every organization like to grow. Nobody wants to stick to one market and this particular report helps any organization to understand certain element which they need to focus when they are going in new market. Studying growth and development for a firm is very necessary. It correlates with organization's size and age until it leaves and its contribution and expansion. The growth strategy in general contributes in the following manner: -

- It increases company's bottom line over time.
- It builds new critical capability.
- It helps in product improvement.
- It helps in improving business strategic positioning.
- It leverages the company's value chain.
- It will enhance the planning strategy.
- It teaches cost optimization.
- It produces attractive Return of Investment (ROI).
- It helps in further expansion.
- Helpful in targeting customer segmentation.

V. GLOBALIZATION AND IT'S IMPACT ON BUSINESS

To survive and thrive, multinational corporations have had to adapt to dramatic changes and increasing complexity in the global competitive landscape. The Globalized international strategies and academic research on different attributes and outcomes of these strategies have evolved accordingly.

Over last few decades we have seen a large dramatic change over business market, where businesses were largely localized and served more stable markets, while today advances in communications and transportation have not only facilitated the acceleration of MNCs' expansion but also served more intense competition and economic growth. Decades ago, the decisions related to MNC's was just made in the central headquarter but now each have their own. Companies try going global for a variety of reasons but the main/typical goal of it is and always will be is company growth or expansion. When a company hires international employees or searches for new markets abroad, an international strategy can help diversify and expand a business. Seeing the pace of growth of globalization in market it seems after a decade the market would be something else from what we see now.

VI. IMPLICATIONS

The present study broke down how various organizations looked forward for growth and being global. The study re-shapes the mode of working and tried to add new strategies and values for the fulfillment desired output. A Firm's competency to trade goods and services internationally, transfer their production to other countries, and pick up the knowledge from abroad on the efficiency of operation. It has been growing due to the technological advancement, rising earnings, and most importantly expertise in every field.

VII. RESULTS & FINDINGS

The major actions adopted by the above-mentioned organizations are:

- The best way to start a new journey is to hold up your experience. Every experience will guide to be better ready for next time.
- Let the resources around you be your business model, make proper use of it.
- Don't just stick to a place, try moving out of comfort zone.
- Business might come in anyone's hand but wouldn't stay with everyone, making use of opportunity is what matters.
- Look for creating your presence. Creating self-picture is much important to grow a business, once the owner losses out his name and fame, once he gets bad reputation no one is going to ask them.
- A good business man always goes with trend with different marketing strategies.
- Employee satisfaction can make production faster. Once an employee is motivated and given proper leaves, incentives, bonus etc., they try to work more harder and provide more output.
- Focus on both quality and quantity, both matters equally.
- Customer's disappointment shouldn't be entertained. It should be carefully judged that customer shouldn't be disappointed by your product. Just try bringing a smile for the customer, once they use your product.

- Proper organization structure, maintenance in organization structure can relate and connect more people.
- Setting up goals. Plan out at the start that where you want to see yourself after 5 years from now.
- Have your own strategies, don't try copying others.
- Don't move back in hiring new employees and kicking out the one who doesn't really matter.
- Make consistency in work place.
- Don't rush out directly, try out baby steps first. Start your organization within your locality, slowly and gradually start spreading.

VIII. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

By now we all know that how and in what ways globalization is important for us as an organization. Growth is important for the organization and one of the ways to grow is going global. The organizations who are going global, faces a lot of challenges in different ways. But they can still be successful by following different strategies like bringing change in organization work culture, proper marketing strategies, going with the trend, upgrading with the era, looking for different newer skills, employee motivation.

Today globalization of many industries is a fact. Some companies are left with no choices, rather to go global. Why? Once they see their key competitor there ruling globally, they are forced by themselves to do it. It might lead to addition of priorities in the market. Globalization is now a competitive game which requires company to leave out the comfort zone and adjust themselves and also learn new things. Staying consistently and learning checks out the survival of company.

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